

The crushed people in Iranian short stories today

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Abstract

The short story is called the "voice only," because the reader cannot do imaginary nature with their. The common feature of the modern short story is due to the presence of "crushed characters". These people have been crushed; have different challenges due to the damage of different cultural, in different cultures. These people are different of a writer to another writer and from generation to generation. Personality dimensions are very important of simplicity and complexity, or flat and round, development or lack of character development throughout the story and multidimensional nature of him which makes the occurrence of contradictory traits and makes him unpredictable. Four short stories are examined in this article that has enough obsessions in it to provide the correct pattern, and is classified the fictional characters in three. 1- The chance for revenge. 2- Persistent and futile attempts to understand the tragedy that occurred to them. 3- Escape from the humiliation of the absolute ruin.

Keywords

Characters, Challenges, Changes, Simplicity, Complexity, Contradictory Traits

1 Introduction

What is accepted as an absolute principle, in the history of short story, It is a lonely and desperate characters. This is the main Anton Chekhov (1860 - 1904) created in the short cape (overcoat) and all later writers, who were just the extender. Thus, crushed and humble people, common feature of all the short stories of the twentieth century. "These people have been taken down, were the product of a closed society" (O'Connor, 1381: 10) who disliked or could not raise basically anyone who is down. Ernest Hemingway (1899-1961) once said: "A man can be destroyed but not defeated." and perhaps that was why he had destroyed some of his creatures. People who they are in any way with this lonely and helpless, the helpless and crushed as a result, illiteracy and poverty in the Gholam Hossein Saudi's short stories (1935 - 1985). People who do not have toys to enter this environment, on the eve of Iran's modernization and eventually are broken down and ruined. Then they want to return "lost innocence" (Asadi, 1381: 27). There are so helpless in the short stories of "Sadeq Chubak" and "Ahmad Mahmoud". Even animals have part of the helpless and demise of the human spirit in the Sadeq Chubak's short stories. In the Chubak's fictional world the dumb animals symbol of innocent human beings. Also in the short stories of Sadeq Hedayat, people are seeking refuge behind; People who have been cursed are trapped in unwanted events. Sadeq Hedayat's Fictional world is full of death and madness. In those stories, there is no sign of freshness rather than birth. Characters in his stories are all passive and just look at everything with puffy eyes bedazzle. Seems, they cannot do anything except look.

"The Dark ... Dark ... Dark is mysterious" (Mandani poor, 1997: p. 8). This is the first of the short story "Fire colors midday" of Shahriar Mandani poor (b. 1956). What is this mystery darkness? Also his people are experiencing the dark space. In the t darkness of thought, (this concept is at odds with a clear mind and not in the term, intellectual), will be strengthened with financial poverty. We see the same wandering and wonder in

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the short story "If he does not have a coffin" And many of his stories. We see the helpless of characters other form in the Abkenar Mrtzayyan's stories: "... My heart is full of sorrow I have no sympathy, that..." (Mrtzayyan, 1999: p. 44). Phrase of short stories "Minaye Man" (my Mina). Stories characters of Mrtzayyan always have some regrets. So they must have other characteristics that to be the source of their relief; Self-deception or self-forgetfulness. As in the story "An Shab Mah Nabood" (was no moon that night) character would be not believing the things to escape his past and always undermines them up to be hard to believe; A self-imposed amnesia.

Without any exaggeration, this is a public space, short stories, of Iranian which is different only with story's space of the world today because the effect is that the public space is the same. Actually loss of geographical and political boundaries of Today's world has destroyed the cultural boundaries. That is why the handicapped of space has been a form everywhere. However, people in the story, have not opportunity to expand According to short stories nature and remains on the surface (flat). The vast majority of Iranian people's story does not find any depth and complexity never; but some masterpieces of characterization, which are multi-dimensional person (round); It can also be introduced for most of these characters in a sentence the characters are one dimensional or two-dimensional in the end for example, gentle and sometimes peevish. They have a property identified and so this property will not change the story from beginning of story to end it. Eve people are not unexpected and unpredictable in the story while the philosophy of modern People being is unpredictable. This thread will be carefully scrutinized in the discussion. But the idea that Characterization method is described to a dramatic, Should have voted for both. In the short story of Iran the narrator tries to silence his voice, loud voice to the character until the character to introduce him. This attempt is more descriptive however usually a dramatized, not deep, according to the story.

In the descriptive method, it is necessary to introduce the characters at least one paragraph. But perhaps the whole story becomes to introduce a character in dramatic way and suddenly do turned a short story to the "story of character". We will see what the short story "A cup of cold tea" of Hassan Tlanzhad, A part of remain superficial character is related to the volume of stories, A part is related to the possession or lack of Ijaz in prose fiction, and both a part is related to the capacity of the story.

2 Research needed

Subject and themes of many modern stories, is analysis of internal and external actions of people. So here trying to be with the following of signs in four short stories of the 80 H.S, that has been very obsessive in its selection, as possible be given to the correct model, in the category of "crushed people".

3 Methods

To stay away from personal involvement and the necessity of utilizing the scientific method, will be used to the general semiotics that signs are where it starts (Todorov, 1382:p. 27).

4 Discussions

(1) Short story, "the moon shining on the grave," Hafez Khiavi.

A): Signs

- The sound of barking dogs of Karim, Was coming. (Khiavi, 1390:p. 78)
- Fear that the dogs go to him (ibid: p. 80)
- The dogs name, was Jabbar and Avaz and Teymur (ibid: p.80)

- He said the dog on the dog owner's name (Ibid: p. 80)
- Our effort is wasted (ibid: p 80)
- Qadir dogs came (Ibid: 84)
- They were Licked hands of the Qadir. (ibid: p. 84)
- I am afraid of Qadir dogs (ibid: p. 84)
- Although I had cast so much bread in front of them, they were not reliable (ibid: p. 84).
- Dogs, were have eaten Mehdi Gholi (ibid: p. 84)

The story is not about the dog but related to the dog is the most powerful signs. These are the story dogs that in a meaningful relationship with people, they are interpreting the behavior and intentions of characters:

- What is the sign Putting name of previous owner, on the dog was purchased?
- Synchronization of the full moon light, the sound of Karim's dogs barking and picking dead grave what are their signs?
- What is a show Dogs Name?
- Why do dogs eat Mahdi Quli?
- Why the narrator is afraid of being eaten?

The people who before had been crushed by another person, also fate, has persistence with them and it could overwhelm them and crush the remaining human identity them. As far as dogs look with surprise and looked ridiculous in them. This is not only brilliant in terms of validity, maybe from a more important order- Which is related to the theme - Imposes itself on the reader. This theme is desperation of an exhaustive human and the captured of events who to plan anything too well, he is unable from controlling what is not in his hands is and within a other ideas is being committed and will be. Mahdi Quli corpse being eaten actually is being eaten of their ideas that are not more like a corpse like Mahdi Quli bodies carrion. Certainly corruption a body is not disgusting enough to deterioration and fall into retrospection of Suppressed overturn a distracted mind and exactly that is why when the narrator and Joseph are laughing maniacally, Dogs who were sure the body of the Mahdi Quli, to what they should do, they were helpless and desperate against the psychotic laughter. Dogs that have to be sure, of the place above the humans in this part of the story, and is therefore probably that the narrator tells their names in a way that rational it is talking about a human and dogs are not dogs, own but, they are human and finally all of crushed people in the story that each of them, are a way suffering kind of mental health problems, and usually are works that it is a sign of mental problems - they are kind of "Eaten by the dog" and we understand well the lack of self-esteem and personality deficiencies and lack of mental balance in this sentence of the narrator: "I said: Lest people meat has tasted under their teeth".

B) The dog is a corpse animal in Iranian culture - Islamic but, has been much emphasis not to persecution animals, including dog But people customary attitude with regard to dog being unclean, Little - and it incorrectly - is far from Islam. So the time when this animal is expressed in irony and the different terms, does not include positive semantic implications. Such as "dog killing" that is most humiliating death, "Doghouse" that is worst place to live, "Dog game" that is most humiliating form of entertainment, "Dog Religion" means having the most bad religion, etc. This customary attitude is contrary to Islamic believe and ancient Persia. However, the dog has a key role in all sensitive places of story and gives space of the dog to the story. It seems the people stories, too, have no flexibility in the moral and intellectual and decide based on their instinct like animals. The instinct here is revenge. These people are displayed with this one feature and are dramatized. Thus, they are naive. Despite these they are well known. Even they have even named the dogs carefully: - Jabbar: is carrier means a tyrant and despot in the ordinary people. -Avas: brings means of Imitation, faultily

and feigned to mind as well. - Teymour: I do not think anyone would doubt that "Teymour Lang" is the one of the few people that they are the most hated for us. Thus the differences an instinctive animal life with a human species life based on thought and ethics reaches a minimum and perhaps even his degree falls to the extent that the dog stands above him.

C) The narrator and "Qadir" have endured the disgrace and humiliation at ones about 13-14 years old, almost the same amount of years that they had dreams of revenge and had no other purpose in life; they are incurred other miserably in the middle of their life now and when they aware from their inability, they leave everything and laugh. In However they state clearly that they have reached the end of the line and they must spend the other half of life to endure the humiliation.

Knowing the identity of the specific names. Hobbes says: "Specific names bring one thing to mind but the overall brings to mind several things." (Lange and others, 1386. p 25) This issue refers to identify the Person's individuality. Thus be addressed to the character in the story as to show that their own as well and not another group or social class and this is what Scholes says: "It is better to know the character of the resultant of two impulses: Individuality of impulse and momentum sample a [type] making" (Scholes, 2008, p. 21). Although the characters have special names, which incidentally is synonymous with function in the story but, the range of names are narrative, they induction the temptation of belonging to a cultural group More than individual part. Another point that is not addressed to persons well and we cannot paint them so that they look like them. A description of a "no plan" is individuals. The name of Joseph is described with this sentence for example: "If Joseph had remained, He did not allow that we bring this calamity on Sarmahdi Gholi." The name and description relating to it, does not correspond with anything, except Joseph of "Sue va Shoon" (Mourning and Whimper). Joseph there is not only a person but also he is a city and even a nation.

2) The story "five o'clock is late to die", Amir Hasan Cheheltan. Inaudible sound except the voice is the narrator in this story. He is suffered past regrets and future fears, a sort of Nastaligh. This is some of the short story the author, entitled "the author in final round up you gets used.

- Who can get used to the presence of a blind owl that sits on the port window of his room, throughout the night!
- Yes, it took forty years to his predicted true. But know that there are other nightmares. Nightmares of a night that sea was stormy or a poor monkey nightmares that his ruffian is dead (Cheheltan, 1382: p.104).

Past regret and fear of the future are nature of Cheheltans stories. The other part:

- You write a letter to the dead as well?
- Yes, of course

We will see this fear of the future, well and clearly in the story that we are ready to check it down little by little. When the author bear all are And beliefs of a society deals with the language of a resolution, who does not know their value and esteem the true artist That part seems to be the weakest point of his story. This kind of narrative and the story was seen making the first time in Chekhov's works. Character is wandering in the space between reality and dream in the short story "sleepy" of Chekhov. In addition, "Metamorphosis" of Kafka shows such a quality.

The story is going to the labyrinth of the mind, personality and analysis. Also, it is showing the problems of a modern human. The man feels, is more than his right. But he brings low in the conflict of events and he concludes in a corner slowly that "He is not like in this life." The fragility and this submission, the way that

delicate and sensitive people to choose it in dealing with coarse and rough life. These individuals have a poetic spirit and placed in a space, such as short stories, they do it too, poetical and lyrical.

Three narrative of this story Include. Descriptions of surreal characters, plot deviate from its evolution, and the combination of vague and mental space of character, with external actions. The same idea is that Charles May says as: "stories such as the realm of sleep".

A worldview. The main argument is that person of our story is jailed. It is imprisoned in a cage in the name of apartment and the prisoner in a cage in the name of his city and his world. Perhaps this is reason that is empty cage his canary. Canary so that is linked to his dreams and the cage that indeed it is heart only and his dried. Cage is the most obvious sign at story. Perhaps this is the cage that in itself has been Rumi:

“Morghe baghe malakutam niam az alame khak, chand ruzi ghafasi sakhtehand az badanam”.

This being in a cage has been an important part of Iranian worldview. This is same cage that first time, Prophet Mani, his soul observed it caught and hoped breaking it and flight poultry the heart to the upper world. Short lyrical of Nima is apparently this issue:

Dar darune kume tarike man
Ke zarrehe ba an neshati nist
Va gedare dandehhaye ny be divare otagham
Darad az khoshkish miterkad
Chon dele yaran ke dar hejrane yaran
Ghasede ruzane abri, darvag, key miresad baran? (Nima, 1368:116)

However, that in the story, he himself, has filled cage. This is central point and theme in the story. Again crushed people, only, frustrated and waiting opportunity for revenge. But why revenge? Who? Why narrator wants cried, be concerned his mother? In dialogue he with his mother, by phone he the form cruel is concerned his mother and in fact this is work that done always: “You want to let us wish to heart?” In childhood both that his mother fear of to create intrigue he and said should not stand at alley he said: "No." Not telling one child to his parents sometimes is more painful than the worst of punishments. This four-part of, is the most important part of the story:

- Mother because him, does tolerate talks rebuke father
- Where with great excitement will avoid of gypsy (Chehel Tan, 1382:9)
- Where at the presence of gypsy cries along cage (Ibid. 11)
- When he rings and speaks about birthday and civil her child (Ibid: 16)

Why likes cries his mother from behind the cage? The answer is very simple, he is thinking of taking revenge. Should someone be grieved for him discomfort. It was decided opponents and the envious forced to breaking silence twenty years: “The next novel will be inevitably that break silence twenty years”. But when cannot, writes novel, for revenge will need to mother's help; mother's concern is cause comfort his heart. But, why is from his mother? Response this is also simple; helpless hero and Timid and the dreamer the story, does not available someone another. Do you know work that is crueller and more unfair of this? He in fact, is always in taking revenge. Our personality which has been crushed, so is Impotent and cowardly that instead struggle with problems, wants that revenge be taken of the all. “I force them that to confess sequel”. We see it in the

frustrations of individual speeches and no taste spoiled narrator: "Time is average timely etc and in such circumstances, it is accuracy so that the average comes face flowers grow" (Chehel Tan, 2003).

When a mother says sentence of "Do you wish us to leave the heart?", A man of all disappointed and even sorrows and worries that her mother cannot comfort him and the writing was disappointed too, noticed that pills is "edge library". These pills are the gateway to Death Gypsy woman he has proposed; Yes, artists and elders are eating such regret and envy and should lamented the lack of them "So all the people! You eat so much grief, so that to be goiter".

A multi-dimensional character. Each story is the perfect size, has addressed the more complex character (round). It is possible to see as a contradiction within the world. You must be careful, because it is covered with signs stating the obvious. On the one hand, the artist's marginal and isolated and quiet, the other an atmosphere of hatred, restless, love driven (with respect to a circumstance which appears three times in the story) finally a heartless cowardice not to upset if you're bringing all your mobile. In fact, the battle of conflicting forces within him that would move the story and makes this effect and the action seemingly without reason.

Showmanship in his speech. There's a brutal conflict between the forces so that break him. What he wants to do and what to do. We know that, in the writing of a novel is that it is faced with the problem of "meaning". His focus is not without meaning that and focus that goes together with the associated endless an inhibitor his paintings also. In fact, his paintings complement her novels. He painted the world is full of signs that together drive and he signs it, the picture is complete and accurate understanding. So he knows that death is the only way it's been the focus point of intersection and appearances. Derrida says, "Talking to God, a worker can be included in the knowledge, not just knowledge of the objects to which they refer, but also knowing how to talk the talk about what he wanted to express. Correspondence between what is said and what was going to say (Moni, 2009).

3) The story of "collecting leaves when they are thrown on the ground," by Peyman Ismaili. It seems that this is a story within "schema" the reason is that most follow Yan Reid and the third chapter of his book of short stories (Reid, 1376: 42). It is repeated twenty times the verb "think" and when the man tries to fill spaces in the puzzle and thus to reach a conclusion. I will not repeat the 20 words touch to repeat the story. The verb is used five times, "I remember" this shows how the memory of man is obscure and faint of an event that has brought him to this moment and to obscure places that repair will solve the problem for himself.

What is the problem? So that what was the role of "the man" in divorced wife? We do not work with this guy who was never known to the narrator. One story or narrative, in this intellectual effort, gets nervous as well as excited. Because of this effort is to open the window and take your head off. This is a clear indication. To answer the original question, the main character of the story is not any clear conclusion. Most likely, the man, his brother, and equally likely, his wife were not too bad. Character, the intensity of shame and awe cannot accept that her brother and properly portray for this reason, we cannot give any indication when more but he knows more about it than us.

There are a number of reasons for that, not his wife and was never queen:

- My wife has taken my hand. [The wife to her likes]
- His wife laughs and looking guests will delight [is happy to provide wedding]
- My wife is looking to me to ask the guy who wanted to dance with her [She is waiting for her husband's permission]
- I wait till he come and sit beside me [Woman waiting for her husband to end and landed on the seat beside him]

- The moment when the man said that two were staring into each other's eyes, no chance at all to his sister and says: wow, she is very good [She would repeat the sentence three times]

However, story character with his wife behaves in the way of her dreams as following:

- My wife is hanging by a rope from a tree and I burn him (Ismaili, 2005: 62)
- Now that she is divorced, it is better now that get myself up and take one hand and a little dance (Same: 62)

Two-dimensional characters. It seems that those two words are enough to understand the answers to many questions about character. In these expressions, to draw attention to a few points:

- Despite the passage of more than two years, he is still involved with his mind open nodes
- Sometimes with viciously hanging out with her dreams
- However, his heart is burning again and would not see her paddle
- On the other hand, should take the story seriously, Character of the work, in its essence is no different from collecting the leaves that have fallen on the ground. It's a farce. Maybe it's the unpredictable nature of human substitute. People in the modern era, has changed its moral standards. Thus, the lack of any familiarity with this situation, do not hope to win this battle. Indeed, it is unlikely that this character can never understand how something that has happened to him!

He would always come back to life: "I decided I'll keep the sheets on the bed as if nothing happened". However, it is not possible for him to return it immediately, while the woman he thinks so: "My wife is wrapped with a rope around her neck ..." and this is the tragedy of our century. People who are vulnerable in a fight with a time that did not know him, they are placed in a path of no return. In a battle between two opposing forces, each day sees more distance with your life. In fact, these two forces are the life force power and revenge; force is always equal death. So long, fits this situation: "He has an OCD person who takes refuge in his own world to escape to communicate with others, but, alas even he does not heal in private" (Payandeh, 2010: 31). Thus, "we can never identify with her. In fact, his problem is not just related to him" (O'Conner, 2002: 29). However, Night has argued against this, but it seems O'Conner has said that more than truth. Night says, "The authors provide our emotions like curiosity, disgust and identify" (Night, 2007: 109).

The story of "A cup of cold tea" Talanejad Hasan:

Synopsis. Apparently, the story is about a girl who has no father. They are very weak financial base of his employees. Female is employee in a private company. In an emotional relationship with a slip and Chastity sees itself as blemishes. Mary was the name given to his work bringing this matter to a head, handcuffed her to a doctor to be able to abort the fetus and the sutures pulled her curtains. Therefore, it is recommended to do the same to him. Ninth day event, three day vacation takes a bloody shame. He has decided to firm up any way you do it. The next day the doctor's office, she is met with the doctor recommended a shame; A half-hour of work, followed by abortion sinful and stitch without the cost! In the morning one day, decided to accept the offer within 25 minutes.

The story begins with these words:

- "It is only a tree. Wind knocks wave pounds granules of snow to him face" (Nejad Hasan, 2004: 33).
- Window opens with pressure as one time. Snow storm creates a wave" (Same: 33).

The first two words, they can tell simply a subject or theme. This part of the story can be compared beginning with the story of Rostam and Esfandiar:

“Agar Tondbadi Barayad Ze Konj, Be Khak Afgand Nareside Toranj” (Ferdosi, 2005: 712).

Apart from descriptive terms such that what 28 remains are related to the action outer. However, to achieve themes, they are cooked and crisp enough but, they show a clip by a weak metaphor, anxiety and confusion and uncertainty and concerns as well. Here, attention is focused on the two things I just got to be the most significant sign of the two. Statements relating to the following two points:

Implications for first point. Mother's note is on the table and below bowl:

I went to work and go to cooperative for the evening. I will be back late. Crumpled notes and keeps them in his fist. . . The mother looks down on the table. . . Crumpled notes on the mother's values and will open. Behind him is a practicing calligraphy.

Nested written with blue ink as:

So that at first loves done easy so that loves Again note the crumpled it and threw it into the trash" (Nejad Hasan, 2004: 34-35).

Implications for second point. "From door goes out ... He walks fast. Not hear any sound other than snow crushing under his feet. The streets are empty. All pedestrians who have wrapped themselves in their jacket, indifferent pass along . . . More heavy snow falls . . . Towards office will move faster"(Same: 37).

Signified for first point. Paper that mother had written on the paper that she was practicing on the other line. In fact, two of the paper is on the differences between her lives. On one hand, there is a normal life with his mother and on the other end of his love affair. The two sides are aware of each other. This ignorance and neglect of the girl and her mother are angry at what has happened blames but just who is to blame is himself. This is because; although the paper is crumpled on the anger, do not throw it away. Finally, when you see that the paper is now on his outward this is the same as his own writings, this time when crumple it up, does not keep but flung it angrily toward the trash. Even stranger is the girl with her mother. He alone has spread to the family and this is one of the most striking products of our own.

Signified for second point. When she is not no other way, after a short struggle, he sees the only way to submit a proposal doctor, he was humble enough and lost so, just to hear the sound of crushing snow under your feet and pedestrians who do not care about him and they still are not going to destroy her. In fact, the price he pays for his youthful experience of a mistake, so too it is nothing of all their dignity. Also, the doctor is a symbol of the brutality of the people of our community; he is still dealing with a defeated man so who needs compassion and sympathy. Without any exaggeration, this is the main characteristic of our society today. This girl just cannot help not to help the mother and the doctor so, he has recited the Hippocratic Oath letter apparently and does not attract the sympathy of the people in the streets, throws himself to be an accident. It is an undeniable fact and it is better to deal with it: "We're good people."

Ethical Theory. Karel Poper says in "Open Society and its Enemies": Always, when obtaining general moral decisions, what helps us more than anything the results of our analysis of the potential adverse impacts that must be carefully and let them choose one. Only if we understand his decision in this case means that the results depict our own specific, practical, and otherwise, that we have decided to be blind" (Poper, 1369: Volume 4: 1072). Two individuals and two fateful decisions so much as to each separately. Crucial, for it will shape the identity of both the also, the show will bring. What will change after reaching the doctor asked her immoral? If

he knows so that by the work herself with great probability, a member sends to the way it is a potential threat and a social harm and the most common cause irreparable damage, discourage you from your decision? Or, if the girl know so that the trauma of what he will and will devalue what honor criteria for his, Do people still be willing to do so at any cost?

5 Conclusions

This is a discussion on the dynamics of human conflict. Mental forces each person to do the following types of concrete facts themselves out. In fact, he destroyed his character may faced with one of the definitions of the characteristics of human truth. Eagleton says: "Since there are a wide variety of goods such as moral courage, compassion, justice, and the like and because of sometimes these values are incommensurable, it is possible to come to a tragic conflict with each other" (Eagleton, 2009: 28). One of the objective facts is human. Humans can cause destruction of the characteristics of a person as a "meaningless ". The outstanding position, which makes it one of the indexes and any potential situation, it can destroy an indicator. Thomas Sas, a Jewish psychologist in fuller definition says: "All human beings are trying to meet the" definition". Anyone that has get to define, he is dominant over the other" (Sas, 1991: 55). In all four stories, all positions are created to the same conclusion. In each situation, a story, an indication of the presence of another would destroy by touching such a definition and provides a large and cumbersome obstacle in the way of his return to life.

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